

Holocol Structure Preoperties Part(20)

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Abstact:- There exist relationship between two functions . Variables play an important role in pure mathematics. There are several types of properties on variables. relationship between topological shapes and variables. There are several types of variable properties on variables.in higher dimensions there is a lot of use of variables. in manifold there is a lot of use of variables.manifold are such section of mathematics which can challenge the pure mathematics. there exist a point where fundamental accuracy break.there is a possibilty when any region destroyed at n point. There are several types of functions.there exist exist many unique functions.with the help of variables we can find out them. There exist fundamental equations in space.

Key words: Variables, Two functions, Euler,s identity.

I. INTRODUCTION

There exist relationship between two functions. properties play an important role in pure mathematics.The theorem is named for **greek** philospher pythgorous ,born around**570 BC**. The theorem was proved many different methods –possibly the most for any mathematical theorem. The proofs are diverse inculding both geometrical and algebra and variables . Variables are not fix and can shift their values according to functions or point. There are several types of properties on variables.In this paper there is a combinaltion all the things. Such as identity, functions, and relationship between topological shapes. Rings ,circles and lines. In function case we discuss two functions which gives us new result. Many functions exist in nature. Lines and curves generate complex mathematics.three is a book on comles ananlysis. Complex function. It is a idea yet. In manifold there is a lot of use of variables.curves play an important role in manifold.

Fig. 1: Circle, Curves, lines

Exist properties in a such a way that:

- $R_1 = R_2 , R_3 = R_4$
- $\frac{R_1}{R_2} + \frac{R_3}{R_4} = 1 + 1 = 2$
- $R_1 + R_2 + R_3 + R_4 = \pi r^2$
- $R_2 \cdot R_3 \cdot R_4 > R_1 + R_2 + R_3 + R_4$
- **Subheading1:** There is a many conjecture in mathematics. many are unsolved and many are solved. Variables are usefull to solve these conjecture. Variables are of several types. Flexibility play an important role in case of conjecture. With the help of variables we can solve these problems. In topology there exist several types of shapes. Such shapes complex and an challenge the topology.

Fig. 2: Circles, Curves

Exist properties in a such away that:

- $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4$
- R_9 is Bigger region of Figure: 4

Fig. 3: Circle, Curves

Exist properties in a such a way that:

- $R_1 < R_2$
- $\frac{R_1}{R_1} = 1$
- $R_1 \cdot R_2 > R_1 + R_2$
- $R_1 + R_2 = \pi r^2$
- $R_1 - R_2 = \pi r^2$

Existence of new euler’s identity

- $e^{i\pi-2} = i$
- $e^{i\pi(\text{Odd numbers})} = -1$
- $e^{i\pi(\text{Even numbers})} = 1$
- $e^{i\pi(0)} = 1$

II. TWO FUNCTIONS WHICH IS EQUIVELENT PYTHAGOROUS THEOREM

If $f(x)=x^a, g(x)=x^b$ Then there exist a relationship in a such way that : $\sqrt{f'(x) + g'(x) + f''(x) + g''(x)} = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$ witch is again pythagorous theorem.

- **Subheading 1:** Curves and lines olay an important role pure mathematics. And another section of mathematics.in this paper we 4 properties of figure1 , figure 2. Figure 3. And figure.
- **Subheading 2:** The Euler identity is named after Swiss mathematician Leonard Euler. given by Euler. there are several types of functions and variables. In this paper we discuss properties based on two dimensional shapes an three new Eule,s identity. Properties which is based on variables .In earliar paper we discuss new Euler,s identity.space is empty in a general way. there exist several types of fundamental equation. Many equations are little bit complex. Complex mathematics play an important role in complex analysis. In Physics there are several types of fundamental forces. Frorces are of severarl

types. In algebra there is is lots of use of properties and variables. Leonard Euler is founder of pure mathematics. sphere play an important role to understand three dimensional shapes. There exist many formulas on these shapes.

III. CONCLUSION

Increase knowledge about figure, two dimensional shapes , three dimensional shapes , fourth dimensional shapes and higher dimensions. There are properties which tell about topological space. Increase knowledge about circular shapes. Exist several types of problem in nature.nature works perfectly.sun rotation is a fix. And another stars rotation is a fix. There exist many mysterious equations in mathematics.to slove these equations we need many types of formulas.iyota is a itself unique number. Which means imaginary.

- **Conflict of Interest:** compressed in figures, little bit propoerties and abstract.

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